

AUTISM MANAGEMENT WITH PANCHAKARMA THERAPIES: A CASE REPORT

Meghashree J. S.¹, Varsha Kulkarni², Savita K. Mane³

¹Final Year PG Scholar, Dept. of Post Graduation Studies in Panchakarma, Government Ayurveda Medical College and Hospital Mysuru, Karnataka, 570001.

²Professor and Head Department of Post Graduation studies in Panchakarma, Government Ayurveda Medical College and Hospital Mysuru, Karnataka, 570001.

³Assistant Professor Department of Post Graduation studies in Panchakarma, Government Ayurveda Medical College and Hospital Mysuru, Karnataka, 570001.

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*Corresponding Author

Meghashree J. S.

Final Year PG Scholar, Dept. of Post Graduation Studies in Panchakarma, Government Ayurveda Medical College and Hospital Mysuru, Karnataka, 570001.

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ABSTRACT

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) a heterogeneous neurodevelopmental condition largely seen in the children between age group of 3-11 years, is raising significantly in recent decades, influenced by altered lifestyle, dietary habits, perinatal complications, and genetic predispositions. Modern pharmacological interventions mainly target symptoms such as hyperactivity, irritability, aggression, and sleep disturbances with psychotropic drugs, while the core deficits in cognition, communication, and social interaction remain inadequately addressed. Additionally, long-term use of psychotropic medications is often associated with adverse effects, limiting their therapeutic scope. Ayurvedic literature approaches similar psychotic problems with the term "*Unmada*" encompassing symptoms observed in many mental illnesses, including those overlapping with autism. **Case History:** A 5 years old child

presented with complaints of impaired social interaction, repetitive hand movements, speech delay, hyperactivity, and poor eye contact visited NIHMANS Bangalore and diagnosed as autism and took medication but there was no improvement so visited GAMC&H Mysuru.

Materials and methods: He was treated with *Sarvanaga Abhyana*, *Shastikashali Pinda Sweda*, *Talapotichill*, *Matra Basti*, *Shamana* and *Shodana* therapies. **Result:** The result of

this case is analyzed and discussed based on the M-CHAT - R scale (Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers Revised) observed the significant changes. **Conclusion:** These panchakarma treatments demonstrated benefits for the autistic child by improving social interaction skills, speech development and reducing the hyperactivity.

INTRODUCTION

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a complex neurodevelopmental condition. It is characterized by persistent challenges in social communication and interaction, alongside restricted, repetitive patterns of behavior, and delayed speech.^[1] These characteristics can manifest in a wide range of ways, from mild to severe, hence the term "spectrum" is given. It is estimated that worldwide, approximately 1 in 100 ^[2] children are diagnosed as autism with Male: Female ratio estimated at 4:1.^[3]

Symptoms typically emerge in early childhood, often before the age of three, while there's no single known cause but there is multifactorial interplay of genetic predispositions and environmental factors like advanced parental age, perinatal exposure to certain toxins (e.g. Harmful pesticides), maternal conditions during pregnancy (e.g. Thyroid dysfunction, diabetes, obesity), extreme prematurity, and very low birth weight. Early diagnosis and intervention can significantly improve outcomes, helping individuals with autism developing the social skills. It's important to note that autism is not an illness to be cured, but rather a different way of brain functioning.

When autism is approached through the lens of Ayurveda the symptoms of autism and *Unmada* runs parallelly. As per *Acharya Charaka Unmada* is described as a derangement or "*Vibhrama*" of *Manas* (mental functioning), *Buddhi* (application of knowledge), *Samjna* (perception), *Jnana* (knowledge), *Smriti* (memory), *Bhakti* (desires), *Sheela* (conduct), *Chesta* (behavior), and *Achara* (socio-cultural activities).^[4]

Hence the treatment principal of *Unmada* is adopted here among them *Panchakarma chikitsa Bahya* and *Abhyantara Snehana, Swedana, Shirolepa, Basti* and other *Shamana Aushadis* are selected in this case.

Especially considering the projected increase of autism is early childhood, successful outcomes in the treatment of autism should focus not only on halting symptoms progression

but also on improving social skills, memory, language and enhancing the overall quality of life for affected individuals.

Therefore, integrating traditional Ayurvedic principles with modern medical approaches could provide a promising result for the effective management of autism.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Brief Case history

A five-year-old male child was having the complaints of impaired social interaction, repetitive hand movements, speech delay, hyperactivity, and poor eye contact. Notably, during covid period patient was reportedly addicted to mobile devices, and these symptoms were observed to be more aggravated. For the same reason patient visited NIMHANS and diagnosed as autism and took treatment for the same but there was no improvement, so visited our hospital for the same complaints.

Family history: There is no reported history of consanguinity and other mental disorders within the family.

Birth history: The patient was born at term (36 weeks) via LSCS, with an immediate birth cry and a birth weight of 2.8 kg.

Developmental History: reveals delayed milestones, with head control achieved at 5 months, turning over at 7 months, sitting at 9 months, crawling at 1 year, and walking at 1.5 years; bowel and bladder control have not yet been achieved.

Maternal History: mother had hypothyroidism in the past 7 years (prior to pregnancy), for which she was under medication, and also experienced a dengue fever at the 7th month of pregnancy.

Clinical Findings

General Examination

Built - moderately nourished

Pallor - absent

Icterus -absent

Clubbing - absent

Cyanosis - absent

Lymphadenopathy- absent

Edema - absent

Ashtha Sthana Pariksha

Nadi – 87 bpm, *Vata-Pitta*,

Mala - once/day, normal consistency

Mutra - 4-5 times /day

Jivha - *Alipta*

Shabda – *Vikrutha* (hypersensitive – closes ear for even cooker sound)

Sparsha – *Vikrutha* (hypersensitive - dislike to wear tight cloths, get irritated to oil application)

Drik – *Vikrutha* (hyposensitive -stare at spinning objects, poor eye contact)

Akriti – *Madhyama*

Systemic Examination

CVS - S1, S2 heard and no other added sounds

RS - Normal vesicular breathing was heard and no other abnormal sounds were heard

CNS - Conscious, but not oriented to time place thing, cranial nerves are intact.

Higher Mental Function

Attention/concentration: poor

Orientation: absent

Memory: Fair

Sensory skills

Auditory: hypersensitive (closes ear for cooker sound)

Auditory stimulation: present (respond for steel plate fall)

Visual: hyposensitive (stare at spinning objects, poor eye contact)

Tactile: hypersensitive (dislike for massage, doesn't like to wear tight cloths)

Gustatory: eats only hard/crispy food dislikes liquid food

Olfactory: respond for good and bad smell

Social & emotional skills

Response to name: inconsistent

Recognition of parents: absent

Peer group interaction: poor

And other assessment made on the basis of M-CHART.

Behavioural skills

Hyperactivity

Temper tantrums

No self-injuries

Stereotypic hand movements

Always moving from place to place

Speech/language

Babbling: > 1 year

First word: 3.5 year (Biyllabic words ma ma, pa pa)

First sentence: not achieved

Child utters single vowel sounds like ooh, aah, and also kuku sounds like birds

Table no 1: Corelation of clinical symptoms of this patient and symptoms of *Unmada*.^[5]

Clinical features of the patient	<i>Unmada lakshana</i>	<i>Dosha involvement</i>
Running around Sounds like musical instruments Stereotypic hand movements Irrelevant speech(sound) & movement	<i>Parisaranam Ajasram परिसरणमजस्रम्</i> <i>Veena vamsha shanka shamyā tala shabdha anukarana</i> वीणावंशशङ्खशम्यातालशब्दानुकरण <i>Hastena vadana हस्तेन वादनं</i> <i>Vagvikshepa</i>	<i>Vata</i>
Intolerance, irritation Anger	<i>Amarsha Krodha</i>	<i>Pitta</i>
Like to be alone Delay in speech	<i>Sthanam ekadesha</i> <i>Vak Chesta Mandha</i>	<i>Kapha</i>

From the above mentioned we can say that this case is *Vatapradhana Tridoshaja Unmada*

Table no 2: Samprathi Ghatakas.

<i>Samprapti Ghatakas</i>	Factors involved	<i>Samprapti Vighatanam Chikitsa adopted here</i>
<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Vata Pradhana Tridosha</i> <i>Manasika Dosha –Rajas, Tamas</i>	<i>Snehana, Swedana, Basti</i>
<i>Dushya</i>	<i>Rasa</i>	<i>Deepana Pachana</i>
<i>Srotas</i>	<i>Manovaha Srotas</i>	<i>Medhya Dravyas</i>
<i>Nidhana</i>	<i>Mathru Aahravihara and Mithyavihara of child (Mobile addiction)</i>	<i>Nidhanaparivarjana</i>
<i>Adhistana</i>	<i>Hridaya & Manas</i>	<i>Medhya</i>
<i>Rogamarga</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>	<i>Lepa (Talapotchil)</i>
<i>Vyakta Sthana</i>	<i>Sarva Sharira</i>	<i>Panchakarama</i> <i>Satvavajaya Chikitsa</i>
<i>Sadhyasadyata</i>	<i>Yapya</i>	Long term intervention

Table no 3: Treatment adopted in this patient.

<i>Chikitsa</i>	Duration
<i>Ajamoodadi Choorna</i> ¼ tsp + <i>Gho Ghrita</i> BD B/F	28/3/25 - 13/3/25 (14 days)
<i>Sarvanga Abhyanga</i> with <i>Ksheerabala Taila</i>	28/3/25 – 13/3/25 (14 days)
<i>Shastika Shali Pinda Sweda</i>	28/3/25 – 13/3/25 (14 days)
<i>Talapotichil</i> (paste prepared with <i>Takra Musta Amalaka, Bhrami</i>)	28/3/25 – 13/3/25 (14 days)
<i>Matra Basti</i> with <i>Ashwagandha Bala Lakshadi Taila</i> 10 ml	28/3/25 – 13/3/25 (14 days)
<i>Jivha Nirlekhana</i> with <i>Kalyana Avlehya</i> (<i>Vacha, Bhrami, Yastimadhu, Pippali</i> with <i>Jambeera Swarasa</i> and honey)	30/3/25 – 30/4/25 (1month)
<i>Bhrami Ghrita</i> (2tsp @ morning & evening, <i>Kshudha Kala</i>)	30/3/25 - 31/5/25 (2 month)
<i>Ksheera Bala</i> 101 capsule 1BD A/F	30/3/25 – 31/5/25 (2 month)

Assessment Criteria**Table No. 4: (M-CHAT-R) MODIFIED CHECKLIST FOR AUTISM IN TODDLERS REVISED.^[6]**

s/n	Stimulus	Response before treatment	Response after treatment
1	Does your child enjoy being swung, bounced on your knee, etc.?	No	No
2	Does your child take an interest in other children?	No	Yes
3	Does your child like to climbing on things such as upstairs?	Yes	Yes
4	Does your child enjoy playing peek-a-boo/hide seek?	No	No
5	Does your child ever pretend, for example, to talk on phone or take care of doll?	No	Yes
6	Does your child ever use his or her index finger to point, to ask for something?	No	Yes
7	Does your child ever use his/her index finger to point, to indicate interest in something?	No	Yes
8	Can your child play properly with toy without just mouthing, dropping them?	Yes	Yes
9	Does your child ever seem oversensitive to noise?	Yes	No
10	Dose your child ever bring objects to you (parent) to show you something?	No	Yes
11	Does your child look you in eye for more than a second or two?	Yes	Yes
12	Does your child smile in response to your face or your smile?	Yes	Yes
13	Does your child imitate you (e.g. you make a face- will your child imitate it)?	No	Yes
14	Does your child respond to his/her name when you call?	No	Yes
15	If you point at a toy across the room, does your child look?	No	Yes
16	Does your child walk?	Yes	Yes
17	Does your child look at things you are looking at?	Yes	Yes
18	Does your child make unusual finger movements near his/her face?	Yes	No
19	Does your child try to attract your attention to his/her own activity?	No	No
20	Does your child understand what people say?	No	Yes

Before treatment M- CHAT Score – 8/20

After treatment M- CHAT Score – 14/20

More improvement is seen in social interaction, initiation of speech responses, reduction of hyperactivity, and normalization of sensory integration.

Image no 1: Image of autism Patient with *Talapotichil*.

DISCUSSION

Autism is one of the main concerns of pediatrics in the present era. This neurodevelopmental disorder of unknown etiology begins in early childhood. The features of Autism are much similar to that of *Unmada*. Due to various etiological factors, the conjunction between *Atma* and *Manas* is disrupted resulting in the vitiation of *Manovaha Srotas*, along with the vitiation of *Tridoshas (Vata Pradhana)*. Due to this *Dhee, Dhriti* and *Smriti* and the imbalance of *Kala, Artha* and *Karma* which results into improper contact of the senses with their objectives (*Asatmendriyartha Samyoga*) and give rise to inattention, hyperactivity and impulsivity. A systematic Ayurvedic treatment consisting primarily of *Vata Pradhana Chikitsa* with *Snehana-Swedana, Sroto-Sodhana, Basti Brumhana* (nourishing treatments) and *Medhya Rasayana* given considerable relief of the condition.

Sarvanga abhyanga – *Sparsana Indriya* (touch) the first and most developed sense in children. In autism, *Sparsana Indriya* often shows abnormalities (hypersensitivity / hyposensitivity). As the *Acharya Charaka* quoted that “*Sparsendriyam Tvagasritam*”(Sense of touch resides in skin). “*Sparshane Sparshanendriye Vayur Adhikha*” [7] (In the sense of touch, Vata is the most dominant), “*Twachyam parama abhyangam* “Since *Abhyanga* acts directly on skin, it modulates sensory function at the root. Many research study has showed that *Abhyanga* does activation of skin mechanoreceptors (touch receptors) by stimulates tactile receptors and signals travel via dorsal column & spinothalamic pathways to brain. Repeated stimulation of this normalizes hypersensitivity or hyposensitivity. *Abhyanga* with *Ksheerabala Taila* which is *Madhura, Snigdha, Mrdu* nourish *Indriya, Majja Dhatu, Ojas* and pacifies the *Vata*.

Talapotichil- *Shiras* is considered as *Uttamanga* (supreme part of body) where all the *Indriyas* resides in it. *Acharya Sushruta* mentions that the *Shiras* is the site of *Buddhi*. *Sadhaka Pitta, Tarpaka Kapha, and Praṇa Vayu* also reside in the *Shiras* and play a crucial

role in the proper functioning of *Buddhi*. In *Unmada* these doshas become hampered/vitiated, leading to disturbances in mental faculties. To correct this imbalance *Talapotchil*, a modified form of *Shirolepa* and *Shiropichu* is applied.

Table No. 5: Rasapanchakas, phytoconstituents and action of drugs used in *Talapotchil*.

Drug	Rasapanchakas	Phytoconstituents and its action
<i>Takra</i>	<i>Rasa – Amla Kashaya, Vipaka - Madhura</i> <i>Guna- Ruksha, Vikasi, Sandra, Srotovishodaka</i> <i>Virya – Ushna, Doshaghna- Vatakaphahara</i>	lactic acid, SCFAs, tryptophan, bioactive peptides, B-vitamins, these exert systemic anti-inflammatory, neurotransmitter-modulating, and neuro-calming effects, contributing to improvement in autism spectrum disorders
<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Amla Pradhana Pancha Rasa (except Lavana), Virya - Sheeta, Vipaka - Madhura</i> <i>Doshaghna- Tridosahara. Medya, Rasayana, Chakshushya</i>	Vitamin c produces norepinephrine which improves brain functions ^[8]
<i>Musta</i>	<i>Rasa -Tikta, Katu Kashaya</i> <i>Guna – Laghu, Vipaka – Katu, Veerya- Sheeta</i> <i>Doshaghna – Kaphapitta. Medhya</i>	Eugenol (calms the mind) ^[9]
<i>Bhrami</i>	<i>Rasa- Tikta, Kashaya, vipaka- Madhura</i> <i>Guna- Laghu, Virya- Sheeta</i> <i>Doshaghna – Kaphapittahara</i> <i>Pradhava – Medhya, Smrithiprada</i>	Bacoside A and D play vital role in promoting healthy cognitive function, concentration, learning, enhances the memory. ^[10]

All these above-mentioned drugs act on hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA axis) thereby reducing anxiety and irritability in autism.

Shastikashali Pinda Sweda – *Shastikashali Pinda Sweda* is a specialized form of *Snigdha Swedana* which provides both *Swedana* and *Brimhana* effect wherein boluses of *Shastika Shali* rice (a variety of rice harvested in 60 days) are cooked in *Bala Moola-Siddha Ksheera* and applied to the body. *Shastika Shali* is described as *Balya* (strength-promoting), *Medhya* (neuro-cognitive enhancer), and *Brimhana* (nourishing). Autism with hyperactivity is linked to underactive dopaminergic pathways and dysregulated norepinephrine and serotonin levels in the brain. SSPS acts through neurophysiological and neuroendocrine mechanisms that helps to restore neurotransmitter balance.

Chart no 1: Flow chart how *Shastika Shali Pinda Sweda* acts on neurotransmitter in autism.

Table no 6: Phytoconstituents and fuction of drug used in *Shastikashala Pinda Sweda*.

Phytoconstituents	Function
Oryzanol	Improves exercise endurance and muscle strength in aged mice ^[11]
Phenolic acid, anthocyanins, flavonoids	Neuroprtective

These properties make *Shastikashali Pinda Sweda* particularly effective in conditions like autism spectrum disorder (ASD).

Thus, SSPS serves as both a nourishing (*Brimhana*) and neuro-rehabilitative therapy, it not only alleviates Vata-prakopa but also supports motor, sensory, and cognitive domains in children with autism.

Matra Basti –is a type of *Sneha Basti* in which a specified quantity of medicated oil (*Sneha*) is administered rectally, irrespective of the season, and can be safely given any age group daily without causing any complications. From a modern perspective, *Basti* acts through modulation of the gut–brain axis. The gut produces the majority of the body’s serotonin, while dopamine synthesis is significantly influenced by gut microbiota. This bidirectional

gut–brain relationship implies that the gastrointestinal system exerts a major influence on mood, behavior, and neurological functioning.

As the *Pakvashaya* is the principal seat of Vata, the retention of medicated oil in this region helps stabilize Vata movement and functioning throughout the body and mind. This action helps regulate the synthesis and balance of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and GABA, which are often dysregulated in autism spectrum disorder (ASD). In the present case, *Balashvagandha Taila* selected for Matra Basti owing to its *Pustikara*, *Vata-Shamaka*, and *Majja-Dhatu-Prasadhaka* properties, thereby aiding in the nourishment and pacification of Vata-dominant neurobehavioral symptoms.

Table no 7: Phytoconstituents and function of *Bala* and *Ashwaganda*.

Phytoconstituents	function
<i>Bala</i>	Ephedrine to stimulate CNS ^[12]
<i>Ashwaganda</i>	Withaferin A, withanolides – neuroprotective and cognitive enhancing property ^[13]

Thus, the combined effect of the phytoconstituents present in the medicated formulation and the therapeutic action of Matra Basti contribute to the improvement of autistic symptoms by modulating neurotransmitter activity and restoring neurophysiological balance.

Jivha Nirlekhana – In Ayurveda, speech delay can be understood under the concept of *Udanavata Dusti* occurring due to *Avarana* by *Kapha*. The vitiated *Kapha* obstructs the normal function of *Udanavata*, leading to impairment in speech initiation and clarity.

As *Jivha* (tongue) is the seat of *Vagindriya*, its stimulation helps to promote articulation and speech clarity. Since *Jivha* is also the site of *Rasanendriya*, drugs administered locally (by keeping *Churna/Leha* on the tongue) are absorbed rapidly, exerting systemic as well as local effects on neuro-sensory pathways.

Therapeutic stimulation of the tongue (scraping and application of herbal formulations) may enhance sensorimotor integration necessary for speech which activates cortical speech centers (Broca's and Wernicke's areas) via afferent feedback loops, thereby supporting verbal expression in autistic children with speech delay. To address this, *Jivha Nirlekhana* (tongue scraping) with suitable *Lekhana Dravyas* like *Kalyanaleha Churna* is advocated.

Thus, *Jivha Nirlekhana* not only facilitates *Lekhana* of *Kapha* but also stimulates the sensory-motor pathways associated with speech production.

Bhrami Ghrita Pana: in this case as there is *Dhi*, *Dhrti*, *Smrti Vibramsha* (impairment) is seen, *Bhrami Ghrita* which is *Medhya* in action used for *Shamana Snehana*. As *Ghrita* itself is *Samskara Anuvartana* it acts as *Deepana Vata Pittahara* and nourishes the *Masthikya Majja Dathu* and it carries the active principle of *Bhrami* (bacoside A, B which enhances the memory) to the *Brain*, *Ghrita* being lipophilic, it facilitates the passage of phytoconstituents across the blood brain barrier enhancing drug delivery to CNS.

According to *Acharya Kashyapa*, the benefits of *Shamana Snehapana* are described as this enhances *Bala* (strength), *Smriti* (memory), *Oja* (immunity), promotes *Dhriti* (mental stability) and *Pushti* (nourishment), while also bringing about *Vyadhi Shamana* (alleviation of disease symptoms).

Hence, in this context, *Brahmi Ghrita* is administered as *Shamana Snehapana*, as it helps in promoting mental strength, memory, and calmness while pacifying vitiated doshas, particularly in neuropsychiatric disorders like Autism.

CONCLUSION

The present case study underscores the role of Panchakarma chikitsa, in the integrative management of autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Autism viewed through the Ayurvedic lens, reveals significant parallels with *Vata-Pradhana Tridoshja Unmada*, wherein derangement of *Manasika doshas* in association with *Sharirika Doshas* disrupts higher mental functions such as *Buddhi* (intellect), *Smrithi* (memory), *Samjna* (perception), and *Chesta* (behavior). In this case, therapies such as *Sarvanga Abhyanga* with *Ksheerabala Taila*, *Shastikashali Pinda Sweda*, *Talapotchili* with *Medhya Dravyas*, *Matra Basti* with *Balavagandhadi Taila*, *Jivha Nirlekhana*, and *Brahmi Ghrita Pana* demonstrated marked clinical improvement by achieving *Vata* and *Pitta Shamana* (reducing hyper activity and irritability) *Manovaha Srota Prasadana* (stabilizing cognitive ,emotional functions and improving ekagrata attention) thereby validating the Ayurvedic framework of *Samprapti-Vighatana* (breaking the pathogenesis).

The outcomes observed through the M-CHAT scale reflect enhanced social interaction, initiation of speech responses, reduction of hyperactivity, and normalization of sensory

integration, with improvement in the scores from 8/20 to 14/20. From a biomedical perspective, these therapies act through modulation of the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis, improved neurotransmitter regulation (serotonin, dopamine, acetylcholine), and neuroplasticity enhancement via active phytoconstituents such as bacosides (*Brahmi*), withanolides (*Ashvagandha*), and oryzanol (Shastika Shali). The lipophilic medium of *Ghrita* facilitates efficient crossing of the blood–brain barrier, ensuring targeted drug delivery to *Majja Dhatu* and *Manovaha Srotas*.

Thus, this case highlights that *Panchakarma* therapies, coupled with *Medhya Dravyas* offer a holistic and sustainable strategy for ASD management. While further large-scale clinical trials are warranted, this evidence-based Ayurvedic approach offers a unique, individualized, and minimally invasive treatment that enhances cognitive, behavioral, and social domains, ultimately improving quality of life in autistic children.

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